

Venture Capital Investments and GDP (PPP) in the Global Innovation Index

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The variable "Venture Capital Investors, Deals per Billion PPP\$ GDP" measures the level of venture capital activity in relation to a country's economic size, represented by its Gross Domestic Product (GDP) at purchasing power parity (PPP). This indicator captures the number of venture capital deals per billion PPP\$ GDP, providing insight into the entrepreneurial ecosystem and the availability of funding for startups and innovative companies. Venture capital plays a critical role in fostering innovation and supporting new businesses, particularly in high-growth sectors such as technology, biotechnology, and artificial intelligence. A high number of deals relative to GDP PPP\$ indicates a favorable environment for high-risk investments, strong investor interest, and a dynamic startup ecosystem. This is often associated with advanced infrastructure, supportive government policies, and an active entrepreneurial culture. Conversely, a low level of venture capital activity may reflect institutional barriers, low risk tolerance, or a lack of perceived opportunities. The variable is a key indicator for assessing a country's ability to attract innovation-driven investments and support economic growth through entrepreneurial funding. The data covers the period from 2013 to 2022.

Venture Capital Investments and GDP (PPP) in the Global Innovation Index in 2022. The data on venture capital investors and deals per billion PPP\$ GDP in 2022 highlights significant disparities among countries in terms of entrepreneurial ecosystem dynamism and development. At the top of the rankings are countries such as Cyprus, Hong Kong, Israel, Luxembourg, Mauritius, and Singapore, each with a score of 100. This reflects highly favorable economic environments for venture capital investments, supported by targeted government policies, advanced financial infrastructure, and a well-established entrepreneurial culture. These nations serve as global hubs for innovation, attracting significant investments and fostering the development of high-potential startups. Among European countries, Estonia (88.5) and Malta (73.6) stand out for their exceptional ability to attract venture capital investors despite their relatively small economic sizes. This success can be attributed to tax incentive strategies, bureaucratic ease, and a strong focus on technological innovation. Similarly, Switzerland (65.6) and the United Kingdom (61.4) demonstrate high levels of activity, driven by their historical leadership in research and technological development. The case of the United States (42.9) is noteworthy. Despite its relatively lower score compared to leading countries, the U.S. remains one of the largest and most active markets for venture capital, thanks to its enormous investment base and a globally scaled entrepreneurial ecosystem. Other countries like Canada (56.5) and Sweden (38.3) maintain solid positions, supported by innovation-friendly policies and advanced economies. In Asia, China (12.2) and India (10.1) show moderate scores, which mask rapidly expanding markets and significant long-term potential. Singapore (100), on the other hand, exemplifies excellence, demonstrating that small size does not limit the creation of a world-class venture capital ecosystem. Countries like Italy (3.9), Brazil (4.4), and Spain (7.7) show relatively low levels of venture capital activity relative to their PPP GDP. This suggests the need for more robust policies to incentivize investment and enhance coordination between the public and private sectors. Less developed economies, such as Nigeria (3.7), Kenya (6.6), and Ghana (4.2), are constrained by the lack of advanced financial infrastructure and less favorable economic environments for high-risk

investments. Finally, the lowest scores are attributed to countries such as Sri Lanka (0.3), Ethiopia (0.2), and Kazakhstan (0.2), reflecting underdeveloped entrepreneurial ecosystems and a scarcity of available venture capital. These results underline the need to improve economic and regulatory conditions to attract more venture capital investments and foster innovation. Overall, the data highlights how venture capital remains concentrated in regions with advanced economies and supportive infrastructure, leaving many nations struggling to attract funding for startup growth.

Venture Capital Investments and GDP (PPP) in the Global Innovation Index from 2013 to 2022. The data on the variable "Venture Capital Investors, Deals per Billion PPP\$ GDP" between 2013 and 2022 shows a highly heterogeneous global landscape. The trends highlight significant increases in some countries and dramatic declines in others, reflecting the economic and political dynamics influencing the entrepreneurial ecosystem and the availability of venture capital. Among the top performers, Hong Kong (+156.41%) and Luxembourg (+113.68%) stand out, followed by Cyprus (+65.56%) and Singapore (+60.51%). These results suggest strong development of startup ecosystems and increasing attractiveness for venture capital investors. Hong Kong and Singapore, in particular, benefit from highly globalized economies, advanced financial infrastructure, and favorable policies that encourage investment in technology and innovation. Luxembourg, with its small but sophisticated financial market, has strengthened its position as an investment hub. On the other hand, many countries experienced dramatic declines. Among the worst performers, Sri Lanka (-99.08%), Ethiopia (-99.31%), and Kazakhstan (-98.79%) show an almost complete disappearance of venture capital activity relative to their PPP GDP. These results reflect political instability, lack of adequate infrastructure, and low investor confidence, factors that hinder the growth of entrepreneurial ecosystems. Even advanced economies such as the United States (-54.26%), Germany (-65.43%), and Japan (-62.78%) show significant declines. These surprising results may be attributed to market saturation or a reduction in the concentration of venture capital investments in favor of other emerging markets. In particular, the United States, while remaining one of the global leaders in absolute terms, might reflect a relative decline due to greater geographic diversification of investments. European countries such as Sweden (-56.23%), Finland (-68.15%), and France (-61.77%) follow a similar trend, signaling a weakening of technological sector growth or a lack of new entrepreneurial initiatives capable of attracting venture capital. Similarly, Italy (-87.93%) and Spain (-85.87%) show alarming declines, likely tied to low risk appetite and the absence of structured policies to support startups. Among emerging markets, countries like Brazil (-82.81%) and India (-82.06%) registered notable declines, highlighting a decrease in investments relative to initial expectations for these markets. This may reflect structural challenges, such as bureaucracy and economic volatility, that hinder the growth of venture capital.

Conclusions. The top-performing countries are: Hong Kong (+156.41%), Luxembourg (+113.68%), Cyprus (+65.56%), Singapore (+60.51%), and the United Arab Emirates (+42.42%). The worst-performing countries are: Uganda (-97.25%), Panama (-97.45%), Kazakhstan (-98.79%), Sri Lanka (-99.08%), and Ethiopia (-99.31%).

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Performance	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	Hong Kong SAR, China	39	100	61	156,41
	Luxembourg	46,8	100	53,2	113,68
	Cyprus	60,4	100	39,6	65,56
	Singapore	62,3	100	37,7	60,51
	United Arab Emirates	19,8	28,2	8,4	42,42
Worse Performers	Uganda	29,1	0,8	-28,3	-97,25
	Panama	27,4	0,7	-26,7	-97,45
	Kazakhstan	16,5	0,2	-16,3	-98,79
	Sri Lanka	32,5	0,3	-32,2	-99,08
	Ethiopia	28,8	0,2	-28,6	-99,31